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The Rich Roots of Eastern Philosophy and the Role of Issues of Forming the Spirituality of Youth in it

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***Abstract:** In the article, the attitude to philosophical knowledge in the history of Eastern philosophy, the rich roots of the scientific heritage of the East, philosophical knowledge, the formation of the spirituality of young people, and thoughts on manners, morality and education are presented. Opinions were expressed about the formation of youth spirituality.*

***Key words:** east, philosophy, knowledge, science, history, universe, human, education, ethics, education, mind, spirituality, worldview.*

It is known that the leading direction of Eastern philosophy is aimed at purifying the human heart and soul, creating perfect human qualities in it, and humanizing social relations on this basis.

At the new stage of our country's development, changing the environment of education, harmonizing national interests with universal interests, and developing philosophical education are shown as a condition for national development¹. Relying on the principles of philosophical knowledge and scientific outlook in the process of education creates important theoretical, methodological and practical opportunities to find new opportunities for harmonizing national and universal interests.

The development of philosophical knowledge created the basis for a deeper study of problems related to philosophical knowledge, scientific outlook and spirituality. In particular, philosophical knowledge, its components, reflections on the question of its role in human life and spiritual maturity in its initial scientific and philosophical form were written by Plato, Aristotle, Augustine, Farabi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Ibn Khaldun, Amir Temur, Mirza Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, in the 20th century. and it can be seen in the works of great thinkers of the East and West such as Abdurauf Fitrat and Mahmudhoja Behbudi.

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Ш.М.Мирзиёевнинг “Ўзбекистон Республикасини янада ривожлантириш бўйича Ҳаракатлар стратегияси тўғрисида”ги ПФ-4947-сонли Фармони. - Тошкент: Адолат,2017. - 112 б.

Philosophy, as a product of knowledge-historical thinking, more or less serves as a common methodology for all sciences. This is a proof of his attitude to philosophical knowledge and his scientific worldview in the continuum of scientific achievements.

On the world scale, the science of philosophy is interpreted as a field that inculcates national and universal ideas into the hearts and minds of mankind and shapes their spirituality. The problems and solutions of philosophy have existed since the formation of the science of philosophy, and it requires the formation of the foundations of philosophical knowledge in the current era, when the process of globalization and fundamental changes are taking place.

One of the spiritual foundations of forming a perfect person is education. A well-educated and well-rounded person is a person who acquires moral, professional, political, economic, secular and religious knowledge and can apply them to social life, and will have their proper place in social development. If a spiritually perfect person teaches others the secrets of worldly and religious knowledge he knows, uses his knowledge for the benefit of society, and leaves it as a legacy to future generations, his faith will be whole and his conscience will be pure. Also, people who are physically, mentally, socially and physically healthy, mentally healthy, nourished by spiritual education, who embody divine thoughts, who are imbued with goals, good intentions and good ideas are recognized as perfect people. The pages of our national history proved that a well-rounded person has been one of the important factors that ensure the development of society and take it to a new level.

The territory of Uzbekistan is a country where science and culture have been developing since ancient times. In particular, sciences such as astronomy, mathematics, medicine, chemistry, history, philosophy, linguistics, literature, and sculpture, textiles, pottery, glassmaking and other professions are widely developed. Currently, scientists of Uzbekistan are actively studying the scientific heritage left by thinkers of the distant past, enriching science with their new discoveries, making a worthy contribution to the development of world science.

Since the first years of independence, our country adopted the direction of preserving ancient philosophical traditions and restoring its historical foundations. In this regard, first of all, scientists were given the task of restoring the original significance of the philosophical works of Eastern scientists and thinkers. Ar-Razi, Beruni, Al-Farghani, Farabi, Ibn Sina, Amir Timur, Alisher Navoi, Mirza have such a rich history of the philosophy of the past, which is expressed in the works of great thinkers of Central Asia. It is important to preserve and convey to the generations the main idea of Ulugbek, Babur and others.

In the 9th-10th centuries, the first scientific institutions and societies similar to modern academies began to be established in the Central Asian region. It became one of the major scientific and cultural centers in the East.

The development path of independence created wide opportunities for the development of science in our country. Fundamental changes have taken place in philosophy, as in all branches of science. After all, philosophy, which has the most ancient history of development, embodies the socio-political views of different eras and forms an understanding of the essence of events and phenomena, not only understanding, but also reacting to them. As long as this is the case, today it is important to further develop the science of philosophy, to carry out reforms in the field of education and training, to form the spirituality of young people, to form the thinking of the young generation with philosophical knowledge and a scientific worldview, and to arm them with knowledge based on the achievements of modern science. Because as President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "If there is education, if there is

knowledge, the quality will change. If there is no education, if the quality does not change, attention will not change either²".

Socio-political foundations of philosophical thinking in any society aimed at changing the social consciousness of the people, serving its ultimate goals.

Today, the renewal of philosophical thinking is not only a change in the general spiritual environment, but also a change in the social image, spiritual world, goals and needs of each member of society. As stated by the first President Islam Karimov: "Philosophy is the father of all sciences. A person who does not know philosophy, regardless of whether he is a representative of the field of medicine or education, art or culture, does not understand the meaning of life and his profession. For example, in order to analyze history, it is necessary to have a philosophical view of each event and process, to be able to draw the necessary conclusions by summarizing them. Therefore, in order to become a historian, it is necessary to have the ability to think philosophically³. Only then can a person make a worthy contribution to the formation and improvement of the perfect qualities of virtuous people dreamed of by great scholars.

The science of "Philosophy" has always been and remains one of the fundamental subjects considered necessary and mandatory for learning in higher and secondary special educational institutions in all times and countries.

In the process of studying the essence of this science, we will determine its specific features and begin to understand what role philosophy plays in the understanding of man himself and the world around him. After all, as President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "Achievements will be ours, we just need knowledge. We need knowledge, no matter what you say, each of us should look back and never forget that we are the children of great ancestors⁴. In a word, it is the demand of our time to form the spirituality of young people and arm them with philosophical thinking. Why, in today's time, in order to enter into a debate with any opponent and opponent, we need to know more about his views, ideas, and philosophy, and if necessary, we should master it more thoroughly than he himself.⁵"

The deep roots of philosophy had a strong influence on the formation of youth spirituality. Along with the formation of human spirituality in the period of independence, studying and researching its philosophical roots remains one of the most urgent topics of the social sphere. The national consciousness, national pride, national pride, spiritual world of the youth is growing stronger day by day. This serves to further strengthen the philosophical basis of our independent state.

Our national values, customs and traditions can successfully implement reforms in society only when our spirituality is developed, because only a person who is morally sound, enlightened, mentally strong, and has the ability to think in a new way can walk the path of independence and development with honor. Therefore, studying the cultural heritage and high spiritual values of our people deeply and comprehensively, inculcating them into the thinking of every person living in our republic, especially the young generation, and raising them to be spiritually mature, selfless perfect people is one of the most urgent problems today.

² <https://www.gazeta.uz/uz/2022/12/20/sifatli-talim/>. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёев 20 декабрь куни Олий Мажлис ва Ўзбекистон халқига мурожаати.

³ Каримов И.А. Ёшларга ишонч билдириш, уларнинг ташаббус ва салоҳиятини рўёбга чиқариш-бугунги куннинг устувор вазифасидир. // Инсон, унинг ҳуқуқ ва эркинликлари- олий қадрият. -Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2006. 117 бет.

⁴ <https://www.gazeta.uz/uz/2022/12/20/sifatli-talim/>.

⁵ Каримов И.А. Ёшларга ишонч билдириш, уларнинг ташаббус ва салоҳиятини рўёбга чиқариш -бугунги куннинг устувор вазифасидир. // Инсон, унинг ҳуқуқ ва эркинликлари - олий қадрият. -Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2006. 118 бет.

A lot of work is being done in this regard at the present time. But there are still many tasks to be done. Implementation of economic reforms in our country requires, first of all, strengthening of its philosophical foundations.

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